

CHALCON DERIVATIVES IN TERMS OF ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Chalcones have antidiabetic properties in addition to their many biological functions. Nevertheless, there is little data on chalcones' antidiabetic effects currently available in the literature. There is room for greater research in this area to improve patient comfort throughout diabetes treatment and recovery. This review's goals are to highlight chalcones' antidiabetic properties and compile all of the previous studies into one convenient location. To alter the current biological activity, chalcone derivative compounds can be created by adding or modifying substituents to the proper locations of the primary skeleton.

INTRODUCTION

Chalcones are the precursor compounds of flavonoids. The origin of the name chalcone comes from the Greek word chalcos, meaning bronze. The reason for this is that most chalcone compounds are bronze in color. Chalcones can be found in most plants in nature, and they are compounds that attract the attention of researchers because they have a simple chemical structure that can be easily synthesized under laboratory conditions and whose derivatives can be easily obtained. Chalcones are also called α , β -Unsaturated ketones. The aromatic rings in chalcone are called A and B. The A ring is the one closest to the ketone group among the aromatic rings, and the numbering of this ring is numbered as the exponent ('), the other aromatic ring is called the B ring, and the numbering of this aromatic ring is classically indicated only with a number. Numbering can be done as shown in the figure^{1,2,3}

Figure 1. General structure of chalcones

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Chalcones can be found naturally or produced synthetically. In addition to their important pharmacological activities, the fact that they are found in very small amounts in plants makes it necessary to obtain these compounds synthetically. Chalcones that can occur spontaneously in nature can contain pyrenyl, hydroxyl and methyl groups. Synthetic chalcones can be synthesized by attaching different substituent groups to different positions of the chalcone main skeleton to form different synthetic chalcone derivatives. There is more than one synthesis method for the synthesis of synthetic chalcone derivatives. One of the most well-known methods is the Claisen-Schmidt reaction. The schematic representation of the Claisen-Schmidt reaction is given in Figure 2. This reaction can be performed by reacting benzaldehyde and acetophenone with ethanol solvent in the presence of a strong base (NaOH) at room conditions. In addition to giving more than one

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biological activity, it has also attracted attention recently due to its good solubility^{1,2,4,5,6}.

Figure 2. Claisen-Schmidt reaction of chalcones

The fact that chalcones have a safe therapeutic range, have a wide range of biological activities, have good solubility and have a pharmacological effect when taken orally has paved the way for increasing the studies on this compound. Thanks to the existing chemical structure of chalcones, they are easy to synthesize, and due to the presence of hydrogen atoms that can be changed positions to obtain different chalcone derivatives and the ability to form open chain structures if desired, different derivatives can be obtained and thus it has been proven that they give more than one biological activity. Chalcones are used as starting molecules in the synthesis of existing bioactive molecules. For example, chalcones are used as starting materials in the synthesis of pyrazoline derivative molecules, which have a heterocyclic main skeleton and are of great biological importance. Chalcones have a wide range of pharmacological effects such as anticancer, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidiabetic, antihypertensive, antihistaminic, antiulcer, and in addition, they have protein tyrosine phosphatase, aldose reductase, and hCA inhibitory activity, supported by available data^{3,7,8,9,10,11,12}.

Diabetes mellitus

Diabetes Mellitus, commonly known as diabetes, is a long-term chronic disease that does not have a complete recovery process and causes acute and chronic symptoms. According to the 'Global Diabetes Report' published by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2016, it is estimated that the world's diabetes population over the age of 18, which was assumed to be 108 million in 1980 according to literature information, has increased to 422 million according to 2014 data. It is reported that the disease rate in the age-standardized global population, which was 4.7% in 1980, has approximately doubled during

this period to 8.5%. In the estimates made based on the data in the 10th Diabetes Atlas, which was organized by analyzing the data of 219 studies from 144 countries around the world, it is estimated that the global diabetes population may increase by 16% between 2021-2045 due to the increase in the world population, i.e. the average age. It is estimated that 94% of the increase in the number of diabetic patients in the world from 2021 to 2045 will occur in low- and middle-income countries. The USA, India, China, and Pakistan account for more than half of the world's diabetic population, and it is estimated within the existing literature that these 4 countries will protect this population in the next 20 years. Diabetes is a chronic disease that occurs as a result of insulin deficiency or the inability to use the existing insulin in the body. Insulin that is deficient or unavailable in metabolism causes a chronic disease that requires maintenance treatment, especially in carbohydrates, proteins and fats, and cannot be used sufficiently. In diabetes mellitus, as a result of the secretion of less insulin in the blood than it should be, conditions such as decreased blood sugar use and increased glucose production can cause blood sugar levels to be higher than they should be. The first thing to do in patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus is undoubtedly medical nutrition therapy (MNT) and to support this treatment with sports and an active life. Another thing that must be done is to raise awareness of the patient and provide the necessary training. Of course, we cannot expect a chronic disease, which has a long and arduous treatment process, to pass by doing these alone. In addition to these, pharmacological treatment must definitely be applied^{13,14,15,16,27}.

Figure 3. Schematic Representation of Known Activities of Chalcones

As a result of the difficulties brought by Diabetes Mellitus and the fact that it greatly reduces the patient's quality of life and the inadequacy of the treatments used today, research is being conducted to find new remedies and drug raw materials for this disease. As a result of the studies conducted, it has been found that chalcones with more than one biological activity are also effective in the treatment of diabetes and give significant results. Some species from the *Astragalus* family, which are used in ancient Chinese medicine and whose pharmacological effects are included in the Chinese Pharmacopoeia, are used in the treatment of diabetes. For example, it is known that *Astragalus mongholicus* and *Astragalus membranaceus* species are effective in the treatment of diabetes. It is thought that this pharmacological effect is due to the chalcone derivatives contained in the *astragalus* family¹⁷.

In the studies, it was observed that the treatment of glycyrrhizin, one of the precursor molecules of licorice root, increased the blood sugar value and glucose intolerance of streptozotocin and decreased the insulin level in the serum. It was observed that the application significantly reduced the abnormalities in the pancreas and kidney caused by diabetes. In the study conducted to learn the reason for this activity of licorice root and rhizomes, it was stated that the biological activity of the plant used could be related to flavone, flavanone, methylated isoflavone and chalcone²².

The presence of prenyl, geranyl, hydroxyl groups, which are valuable groups for antidiabetic activity, in their structure in chalcones supports the antidiabetic activity of these compounds¹⁸.

In the studies and researches conducted so far, it has been observed that the substituent groups -OH -Br, -Cl, -I' attached to the 2' position of the A ring of chalcones provide better antidiabetic effect compared to the precursor drugs used such as rosiglitazone and pioglitazone at normal concentration (210-236 mg/dl)²³.

In a study conducted by Chi-Ting Hsieh and colleagues, when the cellular glucose uptake activity induced by different chalcone derivatives was examined, it was understood that the A ring was an important structure to increase glucose consumption. In the study conducted, two anti-diabetic clinical drugs, pioglitazone and rosiglitazone, were used as control groups. Glucose consumption values were examined in this experimental culture medium. Varying antidiabetic activity can

be obtained with different groups added to the chalcone main ring. Those that can reduce glucose levels to a concentration lower than 240 mg/dl were accepted as active candidates. A Hydroxychloro, bromo containing chalcones and iodo groups at position 2 on the A-ring showed good activity at culture glucose concentrations ranging from 210 to 236 mg/dl. The iodo substitution at position 3 on the A-ring was active and when the results were compared, the results were 238 and 233 mg/dl, respectively. The results prove that the groups in the 2nd position of the A ring (fluoro, chloro, bromo, iodo, hydroxy and hydrogen) significantly affect the glucose uptake activity²⁰.

Chalcones can provide these known antidiabetic properties by affecting different therapeutic targets. Examples of these therapeutic targets are;

By inhibiting the alpha-glucosidase enzyme

The alpha-glucosidase enzyme is found on the upper membrane of the epithelial cells in the small intestine. It hydrolyzes the sugars such as monosaccharides, disaccharides, and polysaccharides found in the food we consume into a digestible form and brings these digestible monosaccharides into an absorbable form from the intestines. When α -glucosidase inhibitor drugs that reversibly inhibit this existing enzyme are taken at the beginning of the meal, the digestion of the carbohydrates taken is delayed and the intestinal glucose absorption is reduced. The carbohydrate that cannot be hydrolyzed is excreted from the body through feces^{19,20,21}.

Chalcones play an important role in the inhibition of α -glucosidase, which leads to a reduction in dietary carbohydrate intake, which suppresses postprandial hyperglycemia without increasing insulin levels. This is useful in the treatment of diabetic and/or obese patients. Sustained blockade of the enzyme by these "starch blockers" results in simultaneous reduction in body weight, HbA1c level, and serum triglyceride. Seo et al. reported eight novel sulfonamide chalcones as effective inhibitors of α -glucosidase. The compounds showed promising activity in inhibiting α -glucosidase. The inhibitory activity, studied by molecular docking of sugar/non-sugar derivatives, suggested that the NH group plays an important role in binding to the active site and the terminal glycosidic ring interacts with Tyr-171 and Phe-177 of the hydrophobic region. Molecular dynamics simulation studies revealed the precise binding mechanism of chalcone derivatives with

protein. Other new chalcones were isolated from *Broussonetia papyrifera* roots and were reported to inhibit α -glucosidase non-competitively with IC_{50} values in the range of 5.3-19.1 mM ^{19,20,21}.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the key-lock fit of alpha amylase and alpha glucosidase in butein.

By inhibiting PTP1B (Protein tyrosine phosphatase 1B):

Protein kinases and phosphatases are groups of enzymes that control a number of essential cellular functions through phosphorylation and dephosphorylation reactions. Among Protein Tyrosine Phosphatases (PTPs), Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase 1B (PTP1B) has received much attention due to its essential role in type II diabetes and obesity as a negative regulator of insulin and leptin signaling pathways. PTP1B is an intercellular non-receptor Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase, the primary enzyme responsible for the negative regulation of insulin signaling pathway, and is also a potential drug target for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. It acts through dephosphorylation of specific phosphotyrosine residues on insulin receptor substrate proteins. PTP-mediated catalysis proceeds via a two-step mechanism in which the nucleophilic attack of the sulfur atom of the thiolate side chain of Cys on the substrate phosphate is coupled to protonation of the tyrosyl-leaving group of the substrate by the side chain of a conserved acidic residue (Asp181 in PTP1B), which acts as a general acid. Chalcones play an important role in PTP1B inhibition and are used to treat diabetes and its associated complications^{20,21}.

CONCLUSION

In light of this information, we can say that chalcones, which have many biological activities, also have antidiabetic effects. However, the information in the literature and up to now on the antidiabetic activity of chalcones is not sufficient. More

Figure5. Chalcone derivatives as PTP1B inhibitor

research in this area can be done to make the treatment and recovery process of diabetes more comfortable for the patient.

The purpose of this review is to draw attention to the antidiabetic activity of chalcones and to present the researches done up to now in a single source. Chalcone derivative compounds can be provided by adding or changing substituents to the appropriate positions of the main skeleton to change the existing biological activity. As a result of experiments and research, it provides antidiabetic activity by affecting Dipeptidyl Peptidase 4 (DPP-4), Glucose Transporter Type 4 (GLUT4), Sodium Glucose Cotransporter 2 (SGLT2), α -amylase, α -glucosidase, Aldose Reductase (ALR), Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase 1B (PTP1B), Peroxisome Proliferator-activated Receptor-gamma ($PPAR\gamma$), Adenosine Monophosphate (AMP)-activated Protein Kinase (AMPK)²⁰.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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No

REFERENCES

1. Abbas, J. "Bazı Yeni Kalkon Türevi Bileşiklerin Sentezi; Sıvı Kristal ve Optik Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi / Synthesis of Some New Chalcone Derivatives; Investigation of Liquid
2. Crystal and Optical Properties." Gazi Üniversitesi / Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü / Kimya Ana Bilim Dalı / Organik Kimya Bilim Dalı, 2023.
3. Gezegen, H. "Bazı Kalkon Türevlerinin Sentezi ve Reaksiyonlarının Araştırılması." Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, 2006. Master's thesis.
4. Burmaoğlu, S. Anti-Kanser Aktiviteye Sahip Bileşikler Olarak

- Flor-Süstitütie Kalkonlar. *Karaelmas Fen ve Mühendislik Dergisi*, 2017;7(2):658-664.
5. Erşatir M, and Giray S. Çeşitli Kalkon-Kumarin Hibrid Bileşiklerinin Sentezi. *Ç. Ü Fen ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi*. 2019;35(6):111-120.
 6. Aydoğdu M. Süstitütie Benzaldehit Türevlerinin Asetofenon ile Kondenzasyon Reaksiyonlarının FT-IR ile İncelenmesi. Balıkesir Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, 2019. Master's thesis.
 7. Çıkrıkçı, S. 4-Dioktilamino-3-Hidroksiflavon Temelli Floresans Problemlerinin Sentezleri ve Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi. Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, 2005. Doctoral dissertation.
 8. Erdoğan, H. "İsoindol, Pirazol, Oksazol ve Kalkon Birimi İçeren Bileşiklerin Sentezi, Karakterizasyonu ve Biyolojik Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi / Synthesis, Characterization, Antimicrobial and Anticancer Activities of Compounds Includes Isoindol, Pyrazol, Oxazolo and Chalcones Units." Gaziosmanpaşa Üniversitesi / Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü / Kimya Ana Bilim Dalı, 2016.
 9. Öz, E. Benzofuran Kalkonların Baskılanmış Polimer Sentezi ve Karakterizasyonu. Fırat Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Kimya Anabilim Dalı, Fizikokimya Bilim Dalı, 2013. Master's thesis.
 10. Güven, Ö. Yeni Tip Kalkon ile Türevlendirilmiş Ftalosiyenin Sentezi ve Karakterizasyonu / Synthesis and Characterization of Phthalocyanine Derived with a New Chalcone. Sakarya Üniversitesi / Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü / Kimya Ana Bilim Dalı / Anorganik Kimya Bilim Dalı, 2024.
 11. Erik, Z. Metoksi Kalkon Bileşiklerinin Obezite Tedavisinde Terapötik Potansiyelinin Araştırılması / Investigation of Therapeutic Potential of Methoxy Chalcone Compounds in the Treatment of Obesity. Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi / Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü / Eczacılık Biyokimya Ana Bilim Dalı, 2024.
 12. Çakır, A. D. Yeni Heterosiklik Bileşiklerin Sentezi, Karakterizasyonu ve Biyolojik Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi. Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, 2016. Master's thesis
 13. Kahrıman, N. Yeni 3, 5-Disüstitütie-2-Pirazolin Türevlerinin Sentezi ve Biyolojik Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi. *Balıkesir Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 2020;(22)1:34-47.
 14. Çalık, A. Diyabet Tedavisinde Kullanılan Tamamlayıcı ve Alternatif Tedaviler: Literatür Derlemesi. *Adnan Menderes Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Fakültesi Dergisi*. 2017;1(2):79-84.
 15. Coşansu, G. Diyabet: Küresel Bir Salgın Hastalık. *Okmeydanı Tıp Dergisi*. 2015;31:1-6.
 16. Meydan, İ., and C. Demir. "Sağlık Bilimleri Alanında Uluslararası Araştırmalar-V." 2023.
 17. Turan, E., and M. Kulaksızoğlu. "Tip 2 Diyabet Tedavisinde Güncel Yaklaşımlar." 2015.
 18. Sevgi, S. "Astragalus compactus LAM Üzerinde Farmakognozik Çalışmalar." Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Master's thesis.
 19. Fernandes E, Freitas M, Ribeiro D, and Rocha S. A Systematic Review on Anti-Diabetic Properties of Chalcones. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 2020;27(14):2257-2321.
 20. Hsieh C. T, et al. Synthesis of Chalcone Derivatives as Potential Anti-Diabetic Agents. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*. 2012;22(12):3912-3915.
 21. Mahapatra D. K, Asati V, and Bharti S K. Chalcones and Their Therapeutic Targets for the Management of Diabetes: Structural and Pharmacological Perspectives. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 2015;92:839-865.
 22. Jalalvand F, et al. Acarbose Versus Trans-Chalcone: Comparing the Effect of Two Glycosidase Inhibitors on Obese Mice. *Archives of Endocrinology and Metabolism*. 2015;59:202-209.
 23. Satılmış A S. Etlik Piliç Karma Yemlerinde Meyan Kökü Kullanımının Performans, Karkas Özellikleri ve Et Kalitesi Üzerine Etkileri. Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, 2019. Master's thesis.
 24. Taslak, H D. "Bazı Kalkon-Kumarin Bileşiklerinin Sentezi ve Karakterizasyonu / Synthesis and Characterization of Some Chalcone-Coumarin Compounds." İstanbul Üniversitesi-Cerrahpaşa / Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü / Kimya Ana Bilim Dalı / Organik Kimya Bilim Dalı, 2019. Master's thesis.
 25. Rocha, S., et al. A Study Towards Drug Discovery for the Management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus through Inhibition of the Carbohydrate-Hydrolyzing Enzymes α -Amylase and α -Glucosidase by Chalcone Derivatives. *Food & Function*. 2019; 10(9):5510-5520.
 26. Gezegen H. Bazı Kalkon Türevlerinin Sentezi ve Reaksiyonlarının Araştırılması." Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, 2006. Master's thesis.
 27. Mahapatra D K, Asati V, and Bharti S K. Chalcones and Their Therapeutic Targets for the Management of Diabetes: Structural and Pharmacological Perspectives. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2015;(92):839-865.
 28. "Türkiye Diyabet Programı." *Halk Sağlığı Genel Müdürlüğü*, <https://hsgm.saglik.gov.tr/depo/birimler/saglikli-beslenme-ve-hareketli-hayat-db/Dokumanlar/Programlar/Turkiye-Diyabet-Programi.pdf>. Accessed 25 Feb. 2025.